

**GROWTH OF SLUMS IN PIMPRI-CHINCHWAD URBAN AREA & ITS
EFFECTS ON URBAN ENVIRONMENT**

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Abstract :

The growth of slums in urban area is one of the major issues for urban development authority. Physically, they display a dense packing of houses and a further dense clustering of population within the houses. This in turn, is associated with various physical and social problems.

As slum is growing aspect of urban environment it is to be studied in detail to analyses its effect on urban environment. This study proposes to analyses the environmental effect in the slum of Pimpri-Chinchwad urban area.

The slums located and growing in urban area causing environmental problems as well as population in slum contributes laborious work in the cities. To analyse and asses these thing properly the growth of slums in Pimpri-chinchwad urban area was studied for the period from 1991 to 2010. The study also helps to understand the urban environment and the basic problem related to it. out of 76 slums pockets in Pimpri-chinchwad urban area. Sample study of only seven slum pockets located at Pimpri, Pimpri-Waghare, Bhosari, Akurdi, Chinchwad, Dapodi and Nigadi were studied to analyze the problem.

INTRODUCTION:-

The growth of slums in urban area is one of the major issues for urban development authority. The definition of "slum" varies from country to country. In India, each state has its own definition of slum. The National Definition of 'Slum areas' was set by the Slum Areas Improvement and Clearance act of 1956. It defines them as places where buildings: are in any respect unfit for human habitation; are by reason of dilapidation, overcrowding, faulty

arrangement and design of such buildings, narrowness or faulty arrangement of streets, lack of ventilation, light, sanitation facilities or any combination of these factors which are detrimental to safety, health and morals.

The physical problems manifest themselves in the form of open drains, disorganized layout of structures and roads and apathy in the disposal of garbage. Social or human problems include lack of privacy, imminent conflicts which are bound to arise when people are in close proximity, almost impinging on the space of each other and a related sense of insecurity. The occasional brawls that take place may lead to Law and Order problems at times. The vulnerability of slum population to indulge in petty crimes and take umbrage in the 'politically secure' environment can also not be ruled out and the dense, impenetrable population clusters of almost homogenous groups provide an ideal set-up for this. On the economic front, the slum Population is apparently the most marginalized. Some of them survive on a shoe-string budget or even a hand to mouth existence, though cases of relative opulence hidden in an ocean of poverty cannot be ruled out. However, generally the slum population is below the poverty line.

STUDY AREA: - SLUMS IN PIMPRI CHINCHWAD URBAN AREA.

The existence of slums can be traced back to the decade of industrialization in Pimpri Chinchwad. Slums have proliferated as a corollary of industrial growth in the area. The first slum survey carried out by the Municipal Council in 1976 identified 35 slum pockets (5621 hutments) with a population of 26,470. The slums were located chiefly around the industries on open lands close to the workplaces. The survey was updated by PCMC in 1987 when 65 slum pockets (21326 hutments) with a population of 96,272 persons were identified. Further, in 2002, the Government under its resolution dated 11/07/2001, carried out a slum survey which identified 71 slum pockets (35412 hutments) with a population of 1,46,054 persons.

The proportion of population living in slums has decreased from 27 percent in 1971 to 13 percent in 2001, in absolute terms, there has been a rapid growth of slum population. The proportional decrease is largely due to the addition of villages to the PCMC area during the past decade and also the large influx of skilled workforce into the PCMC area. While the slum population in PCMC continued to grow in the range of 40 per cent per annum, the slum has been influenced by access to work places and employment opportunities, most of the slums are located on industry/ MIDC lands, along the river banks of Pawana and along

railway lines on railway lands. Most of the slums, 46 out of 71, are located on either MIDC, Government, PCMC and PCNTDA lands and the remaining 25 of them are on private lands.

Major Slum sites in cities are located on the following Area. (Abstract of slums in P.C.M.C. Area-2005)

Sr. No.	Section of Slum	No. of Slums
1	Akurdi	09
2	Chinchwad	10
3	Nigadi	04
4	Pimpri Nagar	15
5	Pimpri-Whagere	09
6	Bhosari	07
7	Dapodi	05
Total	-	59

LOCATION OF STUDY AREA

The city of Pimpri-Chinchwad is situated near the western margin of the Deccan Plateau on the leeward side of the Sahyadri ranges and Western Ghats, 560 m above sea level, on the banks of the rivers Mula, Pawana and Indrayani.

The city is located on 18⁰ 37' 0" N Latitude and 73⁰ 48' 0" E Longitude

To Assess the Geographical facts and urban environmental situations the above mentioned sites are selected for the study.

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HYPOTHESIS:-

The basic foundation of research work is based on the hypothesis. It is a pre-supposition of research work to be carried out on a particular problem. The systematic study of the present problem will be carried out on the basis of following hypothesis.

“Growth of Slums in Urban area affects the Urban Environment”

The Hypotheses focuses on aspects related to slum Population by analyzing the deterioration of environment due to occurrence of slums.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY:-

The present study of slums in Pimpri-Chinchwad urban area will be based on following objectives.

- 1) To asses the Geographical set-up of slums in the Pimpri-Chinchwad urban area.
- 2) To find out the slum pockets located in Pimpri-Chinchwad urban areas.
- 3) Comparative study of selected slums in Pimpri Chinchwad urban area.
- 4) Impact of Slums on Pimpri Chinchwad urban area.

DATA BASE & METHODOLOGY:-

Following points will be the scheduled system of to be applied for this research Papers.

A) REFERENCE WORKS:

- (1) Books and Journals.
- (2) Internet and Newspapers
- (3) Google and Wikimapia.

C) SECONDARY DATA SOURCES:

- (1) Tahsil office Reports.
- (2) Census Handbook.
- (3) Record of Town Planning Office.
- (4) Record of Pimpri Chinchwad Muncipal Corporation Office.

“GROWTH OF SLUMS IN PIMPRI CHINCHWAD URBAN AREA & ITS EFFECTS ON URBAN ENVIRONMENT”

As slum is growing aspect of urban environment it is to be studied in detail to analyses its effect on urban environment. This study proposes to analyses the environmental effects in the slum of Pimpri- Chinchwad urban area.

The slums located and growing in urban area causing environmental problems as well as population, no of hots, Toilet seats, water tab, gutters, streets lights in slum contributes laborious work in the cities. To analyse and asses these thing properly it is need of time to study slum in detail.

The Census of India defines a slum as "a compact area of at least 300 in population or about 60-70 households of poorly built, congested tenements in an unhygienic environment usually with inadequate infrastructure and lacking proper sanitary and drinking water facilities."

Slums are an essential urban phenomenon worldwide and are strung at the lowest rung of the socio-economic array. They are the shadow zones of urban existence where poverty, crime, aesthetic pollution apart from other types of pollutions, disease and deprivation co-exist. Nevertheless they provide the essential labor-force to work in the industrial and commercial sectors of the cities, not to speak of the service sector which can also be stretched over to cover domestic help in a big way. Physically, they display a dense packing of houses and a further dense clustering of population within the houses. This in turn, is associated with various physical and social problems.

The concept of a slum is an evaluative one rather than an analytical one and hence what is considered a slum in one cultural setting is an adequate housing facility in another. A slum can be conceptualized on the bases of:

1. Physical conditions of the area's individual housing conditions, Crowding, sanitary conditions

And lack of access to facilities which make possible the physical and mental well-being of the

Residence of the area.

2. Lack of effective social organization and

3. The social image of the area held laid the community at large as the slum-dwellers.

The study also helpful to understand the environmental & basic problems related to it.

“COMPARATIVE STUDY OF SELECTIVE SLUM POCKETS IN PIMPRI – CHINCHWAD URBAN AREA.”

1. Distribution of Slum Pockets:

Sr. No.	Zone	No. of Slums	Percentage of Slum Area (Zone wise)	Percentage of Slum Area (Study region wise)
1	Akurdi	09	15.25	16.67
2	Chinchwad	10	11.86	18.54

3	Nigadi	04	25.42	03.91
4	Pimpri Nagar	15	15.25	16.74
5	Pimpri-Whagere	09	16.95	11.60
6	Bhosari	07	08.47	17.21
7	Dapodi	05	06.78	15.33
-	Total	59	100	100

Table No.1.1 (Ref. Abstract City development in PCMC)

Graph No.1.1

Above Table No.1.1 and Graph 1.1 describes the zone wise and study region wise distribution of slums in PCMC area. There are 71 slums locates in whole PCMC area, out of them 59 comes under the study region.

2. Population Distribution according to No. of Huts in Slums Pockets:

Sr.no.	Zone	No. Of Slums	Slum Population	No. of Huts	Per Hut Population (Average)
1	Akurdi	09	20014	5413	04
2	Chinchwad	10	28582	6128	05
3	Nigadi	04	2147	497	04
4	Pimpri Nagar	15	19170	5552	04
5	Pimpri-Whagere	09	19886	4412	05
6	Bhosari	07	23377	5542	04
7	Dapodi	05	14937	3907	04
-	Total	59	128113	31451	04

Table No.1.2 (Ref. Abstract City development in PCMC)

Graph No.1.2

Above Table No.1.2 and Graph 1.2 depicts the Population Distribution according to No. of Huts in Slums Pockets. And it is noted that average per hut population is 4 to 5.

CONCLUSIONS & SUGGESTIONS

1. Mostly slums are located near the industrial area which may helpful for providing satisfactory labour supply at the minimum wage rates.
2. Some of the slums acquires large area but contains less population and vice versa. CDP has to execute proper plans for the maintaining area & population balance.
3. Slum area becomes more problematic for the development of city according to standard of living and other day today needs. PCMC has to do planning for it.

LITERATURE REVIEW:-

1. The low priority given to urban environmental of international agencies. Has been explained by “*Environmental problems in an urbanizing world*” (Page no.318) Written by *Jorage Enrilue, Diana Mitlin, David Satterthwaite-2001*.
2. Urban environmental problems recent concern for environment is not only due to natural phenomenon , but the vrba, slum is not wholly an urban problem has been elaborated in “*Geography of India*” (page no. 74) Written by *Prithvish Nag, Smita sengupta, - 1992*.
3. Environmental problems of the area in they live and how the perception affects action at the people has been explain to “ *Environmental Perception of Slum dwellers*” (page no.) written by *B.Hema , shagufta Jamal – 2004*.
4. There has been the huddling of chyters of slum – dwellers in urban areas. The situation of slum – dwelling has become a serious challenge as housing problem has gone far beyond the reach of a poor man has been devoted to explain in “*urban problems and urban perspectivies*” (page no. 212) written by *Gopal Bhargava _ 2003*.